

Beyond Medication: The Impact of Physical Activity and Herbal Options in Managing Depression

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Abstract

Physical activity has been gaining recognition as a key component in managing depression, with its physiological, biochemical, and neurological effects playing a crucial role in improving mental health. Exercise enhances neuroplasticity, promotes the release of mood-regulating neurochemicals, and reduces stress, all contributing to alleviating depressive symptoms. Also, lifestyle modifications, including physical activity, are increasingly integrated into clinical practice as essential non-pharmacological interventions for depression. Alongside these interventions, the growing recognition of St. John's wort (SJW) as an effective treatment for mild to moderate depression underscores its potential as an alternative or adjunct to conventional antidepressants. Both physical activity and SJW represent promising approaches in the comprehensive treatment of depression, offering safe, effective, and well-supported options for individuals struggling with depressive disorders. This review will explore the integration of lifestyle interventions, including exercise and SJW, in depression management.

Keywords: *Cognitive Function, Herbal Medicine, Mindfulness Meditation, Neuroprotective Effects, Serotonin Syndrome.*

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Introduction

The recognition of physical activity as a treatment for mental health dates back to ancient times, with early texts noting its role in alleviating melancholia, an early term for depressive states (Tacchi & Scott, 2017; Tipton, 2014). Modern psychiatric practice has built on this historical foundation, increasingly incorporating lifestyle factors such as physical exercise in the prevention and treatment of depression (Blumenthal & Rozanski, 2023; Tipton, 2014). Research has further highlighted the positive effects of exercise on neuroplasticity, neurotransmitter function, and inflammation, all of which are related to depression. This shift toward holistic approaches, including exercise, diet, and stress management, reflects a broader understanding of mental health that integrates biological and lifestyle factors (Purebl, Schnitzspahn, & Zsák, 2023; Ren & Xiao, 2023).

In parallel with these developments, St. John's wort (SJW), a perennial herb with a long history of use in treating various ailments, has gained significant attention for its role in managing depression, particularly major depressive disorder (MDD; J. Y. Ng, 2023; Nobakht, Akaberi, Mohammadpour, Tafazoli Moghadam, & Emami, 2022; Otte et al., 2016). Recognized for its antidepressant properties, SJW contains active compounds like hypericin and hyperforin, which influence neurotransmitter systems in the brain (Klemow et al., 2011). Its use has been particularly prominent in Europe, where it is often prescribed as a first-line treatment for mild-to-moderate depression (Apaydin et al., 2016; Canenguez Benitez et al., 2022; Q. X. Ng, Venkatanarayanan, & Ho, 2017; Peterson & Nguyen, 2023). However, despite its popularity, SJW is not without controversy, particularly concerning its interactions with other medications and the variability of product potency (Nicolussi, Drewe, Butterweck, & Meyer zu Schwabedissen, 2020). This ongoing interest in SJW reflects a broader trend toward exploring complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) options, driven by the need for safer, more personalized therapies outside conventional pharmacological treatments (Haller, Anheyer, Cramer, & Dobos, 2019; Hodes, Ménard, & Russo, 2016; Moncrieff, 2019; U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2021).

Discussion: Physical Activity and Lifestyle Modifications in Depression Management

Physical Activity and Its Impact on Major Depressive Disorder (MDD)

The increasing acknowledgment of physical activity as a key component in managing depression underscores its growing significance in contemporary mental health care. Non-pharmacological interventions, including various forms of physical activity, are essential not only for the prevention but also for the treatment of depressive disorders.

Physiological, Biochemical, and Neurological Factors

Physical activity profoundly influences several physiological, biochemical, and neurological factors integral to mental health (Ren & Xiao, 2023). Among these, neuroplasticity and neurogenesis are particularly noteworthy. Neuroplasticity, the brain's ability to reorganize itself by forming new neural connections, and neurogenesis, the process of generating new neurons, are positively affected by physical activity (Marzola, Melzer, Pavesi, Gil-Mohapel, & Brocardo, 2023). Regular engagement in physical activity supports brain growth and connectivity, thereby enhancing cognitive function and potentially mitigating symptoms of depression.

Mechanisms of Action

- **Neurochemical changes:** Physical activity triggers the release of neurochemicals, e.g., endorphins, dopamine, and serotonin. Endorphins act as natural painkillers and mood elevators, while dopamine and serotonin are neurotransmitters that regulate mood and emotional responses. This neurochemical release contributes to improved mood and reduced depressive symptoms (Martín-Rodríguez et al., 2024).
- **Neurogenesis and synaptic plasticity:** Exercise promotes neurogenesis, particularly in the hippocampus, a brain region crucial for memory and emotional regulation. Also, physical activity enhances synaptic plasticity, which refers to the brain's ability to strengthen or weaken synapses in response to increases or decreases in their activity. These effects on brain connectivity support cognitive function and emotional stability (Basso & Suzuki, 2017).
- **Stress reduction:** Regular physical activity lowers cortisol levels, a stress-related hormone. By reducing cortisol and improving the body's resilience to stress, exercise helps manage stress

levels and reduces the risk of stress-related depressive episodes (Nowacka-Chmielewska et al., 2022; Woodyard, 2011).

Physiological Mechanisms

According to (Murawska-Ciałowicz et al., 2021; Sarris, O'Neil, Coulson, Schweitzer, & Berk, 2014; Xie et al., 2021), the physiological benefits of exercise extend to several critical mechanisms:

- **Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF):** Exercise increases BDNF levels. BDNF is a crucial protein that supports neuronal growth, plasticity, and overall brain function. Elevated BDNF levels contribute to improved cognitive function and mood stabilization.
- **Cytokines:** Physical activity affects the balance of cytokines in the body. Exercise increases anti-inflammatory cytokines, e.g., interleukin-10 (IL-10), and decreases pro-inflammatory cytokines, e.g., C-reactive protein (CRP) and interleukin-6 (IL-6). This modulation helps reduce inflammation, which is often linked to depression.
- **Hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis:** Exercise regulates the HPA axis, which is crucial in the body's stress response and mood regulation. By modulating this axis, exercise can help manage stress and reduce depressive symptoms.
- **Brain oxygenation and neurotransmitter secretion:** Physical activity enhances brain oxygenation via peroxisome proliferator-activator receptor-gamma coactivator (PGC-1 α) and stimulates the release of neurotransmitters, i.e., serotonin. This increased neurotransmitter activity supports neurogenesis and neuroplasticity, further benefiting mental health.

Role of BDNF and Muscle Contraction

BDNF, produced in the brain (hippocampus, hypothalamus, cerebral cortex, and thalamus) during rest and released by skeletal muscles during exercise, is vital for maintaining neuronal plasticity and functionality (Murawska-Ciałowicz et al., 2021). Also, muscle contraction during physical activity releases myokines (e.g., BDNF) and metabolites (e.g., β -hydroxybutyrate and lactate) into the bloodstream (Di Liegro, Schiera, Proia, & Di Liegro, 2019; Murawska-Ciałowicz et al., 2021). These substances cross the blood-brain barrier and positively influence neuroglial (e.g., astrocytes, microglia, and oligodendrocytes) and neuronal functions, contributing to improved mental health (Di Liegro et al., 2019; Murawska-Ciałowicz et al., 2021).

Also, exercise promotes neuroplasticity and neurogenesis by increasing BDNF synthesis via activation of the CREB transcription factor and CREB phosphorylation, which enhances the plasticity of dopaminergic, serotonergic, and noradrenergic neurons (Murawska-Ciałowicz et al., 2021).

Endocannabinoid System and Depression

Physical activity affects the endocannabinoid system, which plays a role in regulating mood and emotional responses. Exercise increases natural endocannabinoids, such as anandamide (AEA) and 2-arachidonoylglycerol (2-AG), which interact with cannabinoid receptor 1 (CB1) in the central nervous system (hippocampus, basal ganglia, cortex, hypothalamus, limbic system, and amygdala) and cannabinoid receptor 2 (CB2) in the peripheral immune system (e.g., spleen, macrophages, thymus, and tonsils), influencing depressive behaviors. The endocannabinoid system is involved in various processes relevant to depression pathogenesis, including inflammation, neuroendocrine regulation, and neurotransmission (Howlett & Abood, 2017; Huang, Chen, & Zhang, 2016; Murawska-Ciałowicz et al., 2021).

Modernization and Sedentary Behavior

Modern lifestyle changes, including increased screen time, traffic congestion, and a lack of recreational spaces, have led to more sedentary behavior. This shift is associated with a higher risk of mortality and chronic diseases, including cancer, cardiovascular conditions, obesity, diabetes mellitus, hyperlipidemia, osteoporosis, arthralgia, cognitive impairment, and mental health disorders such as MDD (Di Liegro et al., 2019; J. H. Park, Moon, Kim, Kong, & Oh, 2020; Sarris et al., 2014; Thivel et al., 2018). The prevalence of sedentary lifestyles highlights the urgent need for effective strategies to address these health risks.

Mental Health Consequences

Various lifestyle factors contribute to mental health disorders. Unhealthy diets, irregular sleep patterns, substance abuse, and social isolation (exacerbated during events such as the COVID-19 pandemic) can all negatively impact mental health and contribute to conditions such as depression. Conversely, engaging in physical activities—e.g., walking, running, dancing, swimming, gardening, and yoga—has been shown to alleviate symptoms of anxiety and depression and may serve as effective preventive measures for neuropsychiatric disorders (H. J. Park, Rhie, & Shim, 2022; Xie et al., 2021).

Exercise as a Treatment for Depression

Exercise has gained recognition for its beneficial effects on depressive symptoms. It is a safe, cost-effective intervention that can enhance social engagement and self-esteem (Sarris et al., 2014; Xie et al., 2021). Although the precise mechanisms by which exercise alleviates depression are still being studied—predominantly in laboratory animals and some clinical research—the available evidence supports its efficacy in improving mental health (Murawska-Ciałowicz et al., 2021; Suneson, Lindahl, Chamli Hårsmar, Söderberg, & Lindqvist, 2021; Xie et al., 2021). The integration of exercise into treatment plans offers a valuable non-pharmacological approach to managing depression.

Exercise emerges as a highly effective non-pharmacological intervention, with proven benefits in reducing depressive symptoms and enhancing overall mental well-being (Blumenthal & Rozanski, 2023). The evolving understanding of the underlying mechanisms further reinforces the importance of integrating physical activity into comprehensive strategies for depression management. Annexure 1 provides an overview of other lifestyle modifications that can provide physiological and psychological benefits, complementing conventional treatments for depression.

Integrating Lifestyle Modifications, Such as Physical Activity and Other Adjustments, in Clinical Practice

The integration of lifestyle modifications into clinical practice is useful for managing mental health conditions. These modifications require careful integration into treatment plans to maximize their benefits.

Assessment and Personalization

Patient Evaluation

Effective integration of lifestyle modifications begins with a thorough assessment of the patient's readiness for change and potential barriers. Evaluating individual readiness involves understanding the patient's current lifestyle, health goals, and any psychological or practical obstacles that may hinder implementation. This process includes assessing factors such as motivation, support systems, and existing habits that may impact adopting new lifestyle practices (Dineen-Griffin, Garcia-Cardenas, Williams, & Benrimoj, 2019; Krist, Tong, Aycock, & Longo, 2017).

Tailored Interventions

Designing personalized lifestyle modification plans requires tailoring interventions to align with the patient's needs and preferences. This approach involves setting realistic and achievable goals based on the patient's health status, lifestyle, and personal preferences. Personalized plans should consider factors such as dietary preferences, physical activity levels, and stress management techniques that resonate with the patient. The aim is to create a customized approach that is feasible and engaging for the individual, thereby enhancing adherence and effectiveness (Menear et al., 2022).

Collaboration with Multidisciplinary Teams

Role of Psychiatrists and Primary Care Physicians

Psychiatrists and primary care physicians are crucial in integrating lifestyle modifications into comprehensive treatment plans. Their involvement ensures that lifestyle changes align with the overall medical strategy and complement pharmacological or other therapeutic interventions. These healthcare providers are responsible for coordinating care, addressing any medical issues that arise from lifestyle modifications, and providing ongoing support and guidance (Menear et al., 2022).

Involvement of Physical Therapists, Nutritionists, and Social Workers

A collaborative approach involving physical therapists, nutritionists, and social workers enriches the integration of lifestyle modifications. Physical therapists contribute to exercise plans, ensuring they are safe and effective. Nutritionists offer expertise in dietary changes, helping design meal plans supporting mental and physical health. Social workers provide support in addressing social determinants of health, such as financial or social barriers, and can assist in connecting patients with community resources. This multidisciplinary collaboration enhances the comprehensiveness of care and addresses various aspects of the patient's lifestyle (Bharati et al., 2023; Inoue et al., 2022).

Monitoring and Follow-Up

Tracking Progress

Monitoring adherence to lifestyle modifications and tracking outcomes are essential for evaluating the effectiveness of interventions. This process involves regular follow-up appointments, self-reporting tools, and tracking metrics such as weight, physical activity levels, and dietary habits (Lobelo et al., 2018; McClung et al., 2018; Rippe, 2018). Healthcare providers can use these methods to assess the patient's progress, make necessary adjustments, and provide ongoing motivation and support.

Adjustments and Long-Term Maintenance

Sustaining lifestyle changes and preventing relapse require strategic adjustments and long-term planning. Strategies may include periodic reassessment of goals, adapting interventions based on the patient's evolving needs, and reinforcing the importance of continued adherence. Long-term maintenance involves developing coping strategies for potential setbacks and ensuring ongoing support to help the patient maintain the benefits of lifestyle modifications over time (Espinosa-Salas & Gonzalez-Arias, 2023; Moriarty et al., 2021; Rush & Thase, 2018).

Integrating lifestyle modifications into clinical practice necessitates a comprehensive approach. By addressing individual needs and fostering a collaborative care environment, healthcare providers can enhance the effectiveness of lifestyle changes and contribute to improved mental health outcomes.

Challenges and Considerations of Implementing Lifestyle Modifications in Clinical Practice

Implementing lifestyle modifications in clinical practice involves navigating various challenges and considerations that can impact their effectiveness. A nuanced approach to these elements ensures that lifestyle modifications are practical and effective for diverse patient populations.

Barriers to Implementation

Patient Compliance

Achieving patient compliance with lifestyle modifications may involve overcoming significant motivational and adherence challenges. Patients may struggle with maintaining the motivation necessary for long-term behavior change, especially when the benefits are not immediately apparent. Adherence issues can also arise from difficulties incorporating new habits into daily routines or from a lack of immediate, visible improvements in health. Addressing these challenges requires tailored strategies to enhance motivation, such as setting realistic goals, providing ongoing support, and using behavioral techniques to encourage sustained engagement (Collado-Mateo et al., 2021).

Socioeconomic Factors

Socioeconomic factors are critical in the implementation of lifestyle modifications. Access to resources, such as affordable healthy food, safe exercise environments, and healthcare services, can significantly impact a patient's ability to adhere to lifestyle changes. Socioeconomic disparities may limit access to necessary support and resources, affecting overall adherence and optimal implementation. Addressing these factors involves recognizing and mitigating barriers related to financial constraints, geographic location, and availability of community resources (Subramaniam et al., 2022).

Ethical and Cultural Considerations

Cultural Sensitivity

Cultural sensitivity is crucial when adapting lifestyle recommendations for diverse populations. Cultural beliefs, practices, and values can influence how patients perceive and respond to lifestyle modifications. Recommendations should be personalized to respect cultural norms and preferences while addressing health needs (Stubbe, 2020).

Ethical Concerns

Balancing patient autonomy with medical recommendations presents an ethical challenge. While healthcare providers aim to offer beneficial lifestyle modifications, respecting patient autonomy and individual choices is essential. Ethical considerations involve ensuring that recommendations are based on informed consent and are aligned with the patient's values and preferences. Providers should handle these considerations carefully to avoid imposing recommendations that may not align with patients' beliefs or circumstances (Entwistle, Carter, Cribb, & McCaffery, 2010).

Psychological Factors

Managing comorbid conditions is a significant consideration when implementing lifestyle modifications. Patients with comorbid disorders, such as anxiety, substance abuse, or other mental health issues, may face additional challenges in adhering to lifestyle changes. These co-occurring conditions can complicate the implementation and effectiveness of lifestyle modifications. A comprehensive approach to treatment involves addressing these co-occurring conditions concurrently, providing integrated care that supports overall mental health and facilitates adherence to lifestyle changes (Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (US), 2020).

Managing the challenges of implementing lifestyle modifications requires addressing barriers to patient compliance and socioeconomic factors while considering ethical and cultural sensitivities and psychological factors. By adopting a holistic and patient-centered approach, healthcare providers can enhance the effectiveness of lifestyle modifications and support improved health outcomes.

Discussion: St. John's Wort (SJW) and its Promising Role in Treating Depression

Pharmacological Profile of SJW

SJW has garnered considerable attention for its potential to treat mild to moderate depression (Apaydin et al., 2016; Q. X. Ng et al., 2017). The pharmacological profile of this herb centers on its active compounds, mechanisms of action, and potential antidepressant effects.

Active Compounds

Hypericin

Hypericin is a primary active compound in SJW. The compound contributes to the herb's antidepressant effects via multiple mechanisms. Notably, hypericin inhibits the reuptake of neurotransmitters such as serotonin, norepinephrine, dopamine, and noradrenaline, increasing their availability in the brain. This effect may enhance mood regulation and alleviate depressive symptoms. In addition, hypericin has antiviral and anti-inflammatory properties, further supporting its role in managing depression. It plays a crucial role in modulating neurotransmitter systems and significantly contributes to the therapeutic efficacy of SJW (Ben-Eliezer & Yechiam, 2016; Klemow et al., 2011; Peterson & Nguyen, 2023).

Hyperforin

Hyperforin is another critical compound in SJW, known for its substantial impact on neurotransmitter systems. It primarily affects serotonin reuptake by inhibiting the serotonin transporter, increasing serotonin levels in the synaptic cleft. Hyperforin also influences other neurotransmitter systems, including norepinephrine and dopamine, thereby contributing to its antidepressant properties. This compound plays a key role in the overall efficacy of SJW as a treatment for depression. The interaction of hyperforin with neurotransmitter systems underscores its importance in the herb's therapeutic profile (Ben-Eliezer & Yechiam, 2016; Nobakht et al., 2022).

Other Flavonoids

In addition to hypericin and hyperforin, SJW contains flavonoids and other bioactive compounds, such as quercetin, kaempferol, and rutin (Kenda, Kočevar Glavač, Nagy, & Sollner Dolenc, 2022; Nobakht et al., 2022). These flavonoids possess antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, which may enhance the herb's therapeutic potential by providing additional mood stabilization and neuroprotection support (Rizzo, Altschmied, Ravindran, Rutten, & D'Auria, 2020). The collective action of these compounds contributes to the overall pharmacological effect of SJW.

Mechanism of Action

The herb's primary constituents—hypericin and hyperforin—have distinctive integrated neuropharmacological action by non-competitively blocking the reabsorption of neurotransmitters such as serotonin, dopamine, and noradrenaline. This effect increases the concentration of these neurotransmitters in critical brain areas involved in depression, including the amygdala,

hippocampus, prefrontal cortex, and thalamus (Ben-Eliezer & Yechiam, 2016; Nobakht et al., 2022).

Serotonin, Norepinephrine, and Dopamine Reuptake Inhibition

SJW influences neurotransmitter systems by inhibiting serotonin, norepinephrine, and dopamine reuptake. By blocking the reuptake of these neurotransmitters, SJW increases their levels in the brain, which can improve mood and alleviate depression symptoms. This mechanism is similar to that of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) and other antidepressants, highlighting SJW as a viable alternative or adjunct to conventional treatments (Ben-Eliezer & Yechiam, 2016; Canenguez Benitez et al., 2022; Nobakht et al., 2022).

Modulation of Inflammatory Pathways

SJW also exerts anti-inflammatory effects, which may contribute to its antidepressant effects. Depression is often associated with increased levels of inflammatory markers and cytokines. By modulating inflammatory pathways, SJW may help reduce inflammation-related symptoms, potentially enhancing its efficacy in managing depression (Bonaterra et al., 2020). This anti-inflammatory activity complements neurotransmitter modulation and supports its overall therapeutic profile.

Neuroprotection

The potential neuroprotective effects of SJW are an area of growing interest. Studies have suggested that the herb may protect against neurotoxic damage and promote neuronal health. This neuroprotective effect can be attributed to its antioxidant properties and ability to modulate neurotransmitter systems (Oliveira, Pinho, Sarmiento, & Dias, 2016). Supporting neuronal function and reducing oxidative stress, SJW may improve mental health and resilience against depressive episodes.

Additional Mechanisms

SJW also influences several additional mechanisms that contribute to its antidepressant effects:

1. Blocking the binding of gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) to its receptors, thereby reducing central nervous system inhibition
2. Inhibition of monoamine oxidase (MAO), which plays a role in neurotransmitter degradation
3. Regulating N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptors involved in excitatory neurotransmission
4. Downregulating β -adrenergic receptors, which are implicated in stress responses (Ben-Eliezer & Yechiam, 2016; Kenda et al., 2022; Nobakht et al., 2022)

SJW's botanical characteristics and active compounds include the plant's distinctive features and pharmacologically significant constituents that contribute to its therapeutic properties. Table 1 summarizes the botanical characteristics and active compounds of SJW.

Table 1. Botanical Characteristics and Active Compounds of SJW

Aspect	Details
Leaf Characteristics	Lanceolate to elliptic, yellow-green, translucent with a perforated impression; margins with hyperforin-producing glands
Flower Characteristics	Yellow flowers with black dots at petal edges, indicative of naphthodianthrone-secretory glands

Stem Characteristics	Reddish, erect, bifurcated at the top, capable of growing up to one meter in height
Medicinal Portion	Herba hyperici – aerial parts of the plant (stem, flowers, and petals) harvested before or during blooming
Active Compounds	Includes naphthodianthrones (e.g., pseudohypericin, hypericin), prenylated phloroglucinols (e.g., hyperforin, adhyperforin), flavonoids (e.g., rutin, quercetin), volatile oils, and procyanidins
Standardization	Based on hyperforin and hypericin concentrations, influenced by factors like cultivation timing, geological location, storage, and genetic variation

Sources: Butterweck, Böckers, Korte, Wittkowski, & Winterhoff, 2002; Kenda et al., 2022; Nobakht et al., 2022; Oliveira et al., 2016; Rizzo et al., 2020

SJW can be considered for several medical conditions. Nevertheless, its antidepressant properties have been broadly researched.

Clinical Evidence on SJW in Depression Treatment

SJW has been the subject of numerous clinical trials and reviews evaluating its efficacy in treating depression, its comparison with standard antidepressants, and considerations regarding its dosing and administration.

Efficacy in Major Depressive Disorder (MDD)

Mild to Moderate Depression

Clinical trials, meta-analyses, and systematic reviews have provided substantial evidence regarding the efficacy of SJW for treating mild to moderate depression. Various studies have demonstrated that SJW is effective in alleviating depression. Several meta-analyses have indicated that SJW extracts are associated with significant reductions in depressive symptoms and can improve overall mood (Apaydin et al., 2016; Canenguez Benitez et al., 2022; Q. X. Ng et al., 2017). These studies highlight the herb's potential as an alternative or adjunct to conventional antidepressant therapies for individuals with mild to moderate depression.

Comparison with Standard Antidepressants

Compared with standard antidepressants, SJW has comparable efficacy in treating mild to moderate depression. Certain clinical trials have demonstrated that SJW is often as effective as SSRIs for lessening depressive symptoms, with some studies indicating that it may have a more favorable side effect profile (Cui & Zheng, 2016). However, variability in trial outcomes and the quality of evidence necessitate cautious interpretation. Although SJW offers a viable alternative, the treatment choice should be personalized based on patient-specific factors and potential interactions with other medications (Alzahrani et al., 2023).

Severe Depression

The evidence for SJW in treating severe depression is less robust. Limited studies suggest that while the herb may offer some benefits, it is not as effective as standard antidepressants in severe cases. The caution in using SJW for severe depression stems from the variability in response and the potential for inadequate treatment in more severe forms of depression (Kenda et al., 2022; Mischoulon, 2018; Szegedi, Kohnen, Dienel, & Kieser, 2005). The complexity of severe depression often requires more intensive treatment approaches, making SJW a less favored option in such scenarios.

Dosing and Administration

Standardized Extracts

Standardized SJW extracts are typically used in clinical trials to ensure consistent dosing and efficacy. Commonly used dosages range from 300 to 1,800 mg of hypericum extract daily, often administered in divided doses. Standardization is crucial as it helps maintain the extract's quality and potency, ensuring reliable therapeutic outcomes. Recommendations for standardization emphasize the importance of using well-characterized extracts standardized to specific concentrations of active compounds, such as hypericin and hyperforin (Mischoulon, 2018).

Duration of Treatment

The duration of treatment with SJW varies based on individual response and clinical guidelines. Typically, treatment duration ranges from 4 to 12 weeks to achieve optimal efficacy. Longer-term use may be considered, especially in individuals who respond positively to the herb. However, continuous monitoring is recommended to assess the ongoing effectiveness and safety of long-term use (Cui & Zheng, 2016). As with any antidepressant treatment, regular evaluation is important to ensure that therapeutic benefits are sustained and that any potential side effects are managed appropriately.

The clinical evidence for SJW indicates its potential as an effective treatment for mild to moderate depression, with efficacy comparable to that of standard antidepressants. However, its role in severe depression is less clear, and caution is advised due to limited evidence. Standardized extracts and appropriate dosing are essential for achieving reliable therapeutic outcomes.

Safety and Side Effects Profile

Grasping SJW's safety profile can enhance appropriate and practical use. Evaluating the safety and adverse effects associated with SJW involves examining common and serious side effects and SJW's interactions with other medications.

Common Side Effects

SJW is generally well-tolerated, but users may experience mild adverse effects. Common symptoms include gastrointestinal discomfort, nausea, diarrhea, and constipation. Other reported effects are dry mouth, lightheadedness, restlessness, headaches, and sleep disturbances. Photosensitivity is also notable, characterized by increased sensitivity to sunlight, which may lead to skin reactions such as rash or sunburn (Klemow et al., 2011; Maher et al., 2015). These side effects are typically manageable and may resolve with discontinuation or dose adjustment of the herb (de Wit, Jeurissen, & Chen, 2021).

Serious Adverse Effects

Although less common, serious adverse effects associated with SJW can occur. The herb's potential to interact with a range of medications is a significant concern. Notably, SJW can impact the efficacy of various drugs based on its enzyme-inducing properties. This interaction can result in reduced effectiveness of medications, including anticoagulants, hormonal contraceptives, and immunosuppressants, potentially leading to serious complications such as clotting issues, unintended pregnancies, or organ transplant rejection. Also, SJW may cause allergic reactions, which can vary in severity and require medical attention (Klemow et al., 2011; Nicolussi et al., 2020). Careful monitoring and management are necessary when SJW is used in conjunction with other drugs.

Drug Interactions

Cytochrome P450 (CYP) Enzyme Induction

A major concern with SJW is its induction of CYP enzymes, which affects the metabolism of numerous drugs. This induction can decrease the effectiveness of medications metabolized by these

enzymes. Significant interactions include reduced efficacy of anticoagulants like warfarin, which increases the risk of clotting complications. Hormonal contraceptives may also be less effective, raising the risk of unintended pregnancies. Immunosuppressants, such as cyclosporine, may also be less effective, heightening the risk of organ transplant rejection (Klemow et al., 2011).

Serotonin Syndrome

SJW's impact on serotonin levels poses a risk of serotonin syndrome, particularly when combined with other serotonergic agents. This condition, characterized by symptoms such as agitation, confusion, rapid heart rate, and muscle rigidity, can be life-threatening if not promptly addressed. The risk of serotonin syndrome necessitates caution when using SJW with other medications that increase serotonin levels, including certain antidepressants and migraine treatments (Canenguez Benitez et al., 2022).

Other Interactions

SJW can also interact with drugs used in chemotherapy, human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) treatment, and cardiovascular conditions. In chemotherapy, the herb may affect the metabolism of anticancer drugs, potentially reducing their effectiveness. For individuals undergoing HIV treatment, SJW can interfere with antiretroviral medications, leading to inadequate viral suppression. Additionally, its effects on cardiovascular drugs can alter their efficacy and safety, which may impact managing cardiovascular conditions (Canenguez Benitez et al., 2022; Peterson & Nguyen, 2023; Soleymani, Bahramsoltani, Rahimi, & Abdollahi, 2017).

SJW's safety and adverse effects encompass concerns that vary from mild to severe. While common side effects like gastrointestinal discomfort and photosensitivity are generally manageable, serious adverse effects, including drug interactions, allergic reactions, and serotonin syndrome, require careful consideration.

Integration of SJW in Clinical Practice for Depression

SJW's integration into clinical practice requires careful consideration of established guidelines, its role in complementary and alternative medicine (CAM), and criteria for patient selection.

Guidelines and Recommendations

Clinical Guidelines

Major psychiatric associations and organizations have developed recommendations regarding the use of SJW for treating depression. Generally, clinical guidelines recommend considering SJW as an alternative treatment for mild to moderate depression. Some evidence supports the herb's efficacy in severe cases, although it may not be recommended as a first-line treatment. Guidelines often emphasize the importance of evaluating the quality of SJW products and monitoring patients for potential drug interactions and side effects (Apaydin et al., 2016; Ravindran et al., 2016). The role of SJW in treating more severe forms of depression is less well-defined, and its use is typically recommended with caution and in consultation with a healthcare provider.

Integrative Approaches

In CAM practices, SJW plays a role in managing depression as part of a broader therapeutic strategy. Integrative approaches often involve combining SJW with conventional treatments, such as psychotherapy or pharmacotherapy, to enhance overall therapeutic outcomes. When integrating SJW into treatment regimens, practitioners should consider its interactions with other medications and ensure that patients receive comprehensive care that addresses both conventional and complementary aspects of treatment (Ravindran et al., 2016). Integrative medicine combines the strengths of both CAM and conventional approaches to optimize patient well-being.

Patient Selection Criteria

Identifying patients who may benefit most from SJW treatment involves several considerations. Ideal candidates are typically those with mild to moderate depression who have not responded adequately to conventional treatments or prefer alternative options. Patients should be assessed for potential contraindications, including interactions with other medications and underlying health conditions. Evaluating the patient's overall health, treatment history, and preferences is crucial to determine whether SJW is a suitable addition to their therapeutic regimen (Kenda et al., 2022; Qureshi & Al-Bedah, 2013). Careful selection helps maximize the benefits of SJW while minimizing potential risks.

Standard treatments for most psychological disorders typically involve pharmacotherapy, brain stimulation therapies, and various forms of psychotherapy or counseling, including behavioral, cognitive, interpersonal, psychoanalytic, psychodynamic, and supportive therapies (Health Quality Ontario, 2017; Picardi & Gaetano, 2014). However, many patients minimally use available psychopharmacological treatments due to several factors, such as debilitating drug side effects, dependency, withdrawal symptoms, and the high cost of medications.

Studies suggest that patients often seek alternative treatments, such as nutraceuticals or dietary supplements, before considering conventional therapies. This preference may stem from a lack of insurance, social stigmatization of mental health disorders, unwillingness to take or adhere to prescribed medications or therapies, and general dissatisfaction with the outcomes of these conventional treatments (Alateeq, Alsubaie, Alsafi, Alsulaiman, & Korayem, 2022).

While SJW may offer benefits for managing mild to moderate depression, its use should be guided by established recommendations and tailored to individual patient needs. Combining SJW with conventional treatments and selecting appropriate candidates can enhance treatment outcomes and ensure safe, effective care. Annexure 2 provides an overview of regulatory and ethical considerations essential for safe, effective treatment and integration into therapeutic practices, addressing potential usage issues.

Additional Herbal Options for MDD Management

Herbal medicine has become an increasingly significant component of CAM, particularly in the management of MDD. In addition to SJW, several herbal products have been studied for their potential to alleviate symptoms of MDD, providing options that may be more acceptable or tolerable for some patients.

A range of herbal products is recognized for their potential antidepressant properties. Notwithstanding SJW, the most studied are saffron (*Crocus sativus*), known for its vibrant color and mood-enhancing effects, and green tea (*Camellia sinensis*), which contains polyphenols that may contribute to mental well-being. Other notable examples include borage (*Echium amoenum*), valued for its calming effects, and roseroot (*Rhodiola rosea*), traditionally used to combat fatigue and depression, especially in stressful situations (Lee & Bae, 2017).

Kava (*Piper methysticum*) is another herbal product that has been explored for its anxiolytic and antidepressant properties, particularly in patients experiencing co-occurring anxiety and depression. The lotus plant (*Nelumbo nucifera*) and seed (*Nelumbinis semen*) are recognized for their potential calming and mood-regulating effects. Lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia*) is well-known for its anxiolytic and antidepressant properties and is often used in aromatherapy to promote relaxation and improve mood (Lee & Bae, 2017).

The growing interest in natural remedies as potential adjuncts or alternatives to conventional pharmacotherapy displays promise in expanding treatment options and personalizing patient care. While herbs like *Crocus sativus*, *Camellia sinensis*, and others have demonstrated potential, their use

should be based on evidence from clinical studies, with attention to safety profiles and potential interactions.

Conclusion

Physical activity is increasingly recognized as a key factor in managing depression, aiding both prevention and treatment by influencing various physiological, biochemical, and neurological processes. It enhances neuroplasticity and neurogenesis, improving cognitive function and alleviating depressive symptoms. Exercise stimulates the release of mood-regulating neurochemicals such as endorphins, dopamine, and serotonin while lowering cortisol levels to reduce stress. Physiologically, exercise increases brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), supports neuronal growth, and balances inflammation-related cytokines. Regular activity improves brain oxygenation and neurotransmitter function, supporting mental health. Also, muscle contractions during exercise release myokines and metabolites like β -hydroxybutyrate and lactate, which enhance neuronal function. Exercise also boosts endocannabinoids like anandamide, which interact with brain receptors to reduce depressive behaviors. In contrast, sedentary lifestyles contribute to mental health risks, including major depressive disorder (MDD). Physical activity offers a low-cost, effective intervention for depression, either alone or alongside pharmacological treatments. Considering patient readiness and personalized care, its integration into clinical practice can improve outcomes. St. John's wort (SJW) has also attracted attention for its potential antidepressant effects. Its active compounds, hypericin and hyperforin, influence neurotransmitter systems by inhibiting the reuptake of serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine. This mechanism is similar to that of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs), making SJW a viable alternative or adjunct to conventional antidepressants for mild to moderate depression. SJW also offers anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective properties, contributing further to its antidepressant potential. Clinical studies show SJW's effectiveness for mild to moderate depression, with some trials indicating comparable efficacy to SSRIs and fewer side effects. However, variability in trial outcomes requires careful consideration when incorporating SJW into treatment plans, supporting its use as an alternative or adjunct to conventional antidepressants.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that this paper was written without any commercial or financial relationship that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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Annexures

Annexure 1. Other Lifestyle Modifications

Lifestyle modifications have gained increasing attention in the treatment and prevention of mental health disorders, particularly depression. While pharmacological interventions remain central to management, non-pharmacological approaches have demonstrated substantial benefits.

Aromatherapy

Aromatherapy has emerged as a complementary therapy with significant implications for mental health, particularly in reducing stress and improving emotional well-being. The mechanism through which aromatherapy exerts its effects is linked to the olfactory system, which directly connects to the limbic system—the brain’s emotional center. Essential oils, such as lavender and chamomile, have demonstrated calming effects, helping regulate mood and reduce anxiety. These effects support mental well-being by modulating neurochemical activity and providing a sense of relaxation and calm (Cao, Zhou, Liu, Chen, & Zheng, 2023).

Diet and Nutrition

Anti-Inflammatory Diets

Dietary patterns, particularly those rich in anti-inflammatory components, are crucial to mental health. The Mediterranean diet, known for its abundance of Omega-3 fatty acids, fruits, vegetables, and whole grains, has been associated with reduced levels of systemic inflammation. Inflammation has been increasingly linked to the pathophysiology of depression, and anti-inflammatory diets may help mitigate depressive symptoms by reducing the body’s inflammatory response. Omega-3 fatty acids, especially, support brain function and have been shown to alleviate mood disturbances (Kurowska, Ziemichód, Herbet, & Piątkowska-Chmiel, 2023).

Micronutrients

Micronutrients are essential for maintaining optimal brain function. B vitamins, magnesium, and zinc are especially important in regulating neurotransmitter activity and promoting emotional resilience. Deficiencies in these micronutrients have been associated with depressive symptoms and cognitive impairment. B vitamins (e.g., B6, B12, and folate) aid in the synthesis of serotonin and dopamine, key neurotransmitters involved in mood regulation. Magnesium and zinc further support synaptic plasticity and protect against oxidative stress, helping maintain emotional stability (Tardy, Pouteau, Marquez, Yilmaz, & Scholey, 2020; Zielińska, Łuszczki, & Dereń, 2023).

Massage Therapy

Massage therapy offers well-established benefits in reducing stress and improving mood. The mechanical stimulation of muscle tissue during massage activates the parasympathetic nervous system, promoting relaxation and reducing cortisol levels, a hormone associated with stress. Also, massage enhances the release of endorphins and serotonin, neurochemicals involved in mood regulation and emotional well-being. These physiological effects make massage an effective adjunct therapy for individuals experiencing stress and anxiety, contributing to improved mental health outcomes (Field, 2014)

Mindfulness Meditation

Mindfulness meditation has been widely recognized for its effectiveness in managing stress and promoting emotional regulation. Individuals can cultivate a greater sense of control over their thoughts and emotions by focusing on present-moment awareness. Research shows that regular

practice of mindfulness meditation can reduce symptoms of anxiety and depression, possibly through modulating the HPA axis and lowering cortisol levels. This stress reduction technique promotes neuroplasticity, enhancing emotional resilience and improving mental health outcomes (Taren et al., 2015; Yavuz Sercekman, 2024).

Pet Therapy

Pet or animal-assisted therapy has demonstrated significant benefits in providing emotional support and reducing feelings of loneliness. The bond between humans and animals can enhance psychological well-being by fostering a sense of companionship and reducing anxiety. Interacting with pets has been shown to increase oxytocin levels, a hormone that promotes bonding and emotional connection, which can help alleviate depressive symptoms and promote mental health (Hughes, Braun, Putnam, Martinez, & Fine, 2021).

Prayer and Spiritual Healing

Spiritual practices, including prayer and meditation, offer psychological benefits by fostering emotional resilience and providing a sense of purpose and connection. These practices help individuals cope with stress and emotional challenges by reinforcing a sense of hope and stability. The psychological impact of prayer, particularly in individuals who derive comfort from spiritual beliefs, has been linked to improved mental health outcomes, including reductions in depressive symptoms and anxiety (Zhang, Zhang, & Li, 2024).

Sleep Hygiene

Circadian Rhythms

Maintaining consistent sleep patterns is critical for mental health, as disruptions in circadian rhythms are closely associated with mood disorders, including depression. Adequate sleep helps regulate the body's internal clock, and regular sleep-wake cycles are essential for emotional stability. Poor sleep hygiene, including irregular bedtimes and excessive screen time before bed, can exacerbate depressive symptoms by disrupting natural circadian rhythms (Desai et al., 2024).

Sleep Disorders

Addressing sleep disorders, such as insomnia, is fundamental to improving mental health. Insomnia is commonly associated with depression, and individuals who experience chronic sleep deprivation are at higher risk of developing mood disorders. Interventions that promote sleep hygiene, such as creating a consistent bedtime routine and minimizing disruptions, can improve sleep quality and reduce depressive symptoms (Alanazi, Alanazi, Albuhairy, & Alanazi, 2023; Scott, Webb, Martyn-St James, Rowse, & Weich, 2021).

Social Support and Community Engagement

Social Interaction

The presence of a supportive social network is essential in preventing depression and fostering recovery. Social interactions provide emotional validation, reduce feelings of isolation, and offer practical support during periods of emotional distress. Individuals who maintain strong connections with family and friends are more likely to experience improved mental health outcomes, as social support plays a protective role against depressive episodes (Acoba, 2024; Kupferberg & Hasler, 2023).

Community Programs

Participation in community programs and peer support groups can significantly enhance mental well-being. Group activities, such as exercise classes or mental health support groups, provide a

sense of belonging and shared experience, which are critical for emotional recovery. These programs foster connection and reduce feelings of isolation, offering a valuable resource for individuals experiencing depression (Webber & Fendt-Newlin, 2017).

Time Management and Relaxation Techniques

Effective time management and incorporating relaxation techniques, such as deep breathing exercises and progressive muscle relaxation, can significantly reduce stress levels (Norelli, Long, & Krepps, 2023). By organizing daily tasks and allowing time for self-care, individuals can reduce the mental burden associated with overcommitment, thereby improving their mental health (Sawyer, 2023). Relaxation exercises help alleviate tension and promote a sense of calm, which is crucial for emotional well-being.

Yoga

Yoga integrates physical, mental, and emotional practices that have been shown to reduce stress and alleviate depressive symptoms. Through controlled breathing, bodily postures, and meditation, yoga helps regulate the autonomic nervous system, reducing the physiological effects of stress. Yoga also enhances neuroplasticity and increases levels of GABA, a neurotransmitter associated with relaxation, contributing to improved mental health and emotional regulation (Nourollahimoghdam, Gorji, Gorji, & Khaleghi Ghadiri, 2021).

These interventions offer physiological and psychological benefits that complement conventional pharmacological treatments. Incorporating these strategies into daily life can significantly improve emotional well-being and support long-term mental health resilience.

Annexure 2. Regulatory and Ethical Considerations of St. John's Word (SJW)

SJW's use involves various regulatory and ethical considerations essential for ensuring safe and effective treatment. These aspects are critical for integrating SJW into therapeutic practices and addressing potential issues related to its use.

Global Regulation

Regulatory Status

The regulatory status of SJW varies across different regions. In Europe, it is classified as an herbal medicine. It is subject to regulations governing herbal products. European regulations typically require evidence of safety and efficacy, although the standards can vary between countries (Gatt, Vella Bonanno, & Zammit, 2024; Pelkonen, Xu, & Fan, 2014). In the United States, SJW is categorized as a dietary supplement, which means it is regulated under standards different from those of pharmaceutical drugs. This classification does not require pre-market approval for safety and efficacy, although manufacturers must adhere to good manufacturing practices (GMP) to ensure product quality (Hassen et al., 2022). In other parts of the world, SJW may be classified similarly as a supplement or herbal medicine, with varying degrees of regulatory oversight.

Quality Control Issues

One of the significant challenges in the global regulation of SJW involves quality control. Standardizing extracts and ensuring consistency in active compound concentrations are critical issues. Variability in the concentration of active ingredients, such as hypericin and hyperforin, can impact the herb's effectiveness and safety. Additionally, contamination or adulteration of SJW products poses consumer risks. Regulatory bodies and manufacturers must address these issues to ensure that products are safe, effective, and free from harmful contaminants (Gatt et al., 2024; Hassen et al., 2022).

Ethical Considerations

Use in Vulnerable Populations

Ethical concerns arise when using SJW for treating depression, especially in vulnerable populations such as pregnant women, children, and individuals with severe depression. The safety of SJW during pregnancy is not well-established, raising concerns about potential risks to both the mother and the fetus. For children, the efficacy and safety of SJW for treating depression have not been thoroughly studied, making its use a matter of caution (Budzynska, Gardner, Dog, & Gardiner, 2013; Dugoua, Mills, Perri, & Koren, 2006). In cases of severe depression, there is a risk that relying on herbal treatments alone could delay access to more proven and effective therapies, which may be detrimental to patient outcomes (Nobakht et al., 2022).

Informed Consent

Ensuring informed consent is a fundamental ethical requirement when using SJW. Patients should be provided with comprehensive information about the potential risks, benefits, and alternative treatments. This information should include details about possible side effects, drug interactions, and the variable quality of herbal supplements (Forsdike & Pirotta, 2019). Informed consent ensures that patients make decisions based on a clear understanding of their treatment options, which is crucial for ethical medical practice.

SJW's classification and regulation vary globally, with quality control and standardization challenges. Ethical issues include the cautious use of the herb in vulnerable populations and the necessity for informed consent.

